

FOLKLORE IS THE HISTORY AND PRESENT OF OUR FUTURE

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Abstract. This article describes the stages of development of bakshi and national music in Karakalpakstan, new educational institutions in the field of culture. Folk art works are found in the golden goose of the people, in the keepers of it since long periods, in the performers, the people themselves are found as a stuffing.

Keywords: Folklor, national music, jirov, bakshi, dastan, theory, culture of Karakalpakstan, national instrument Duwtar.

ФОЛЬКЛОР – ЭТО ИСТОРИЯ И НАСТОЯЩЕЕ НАШЕГО БУДУЩЕГО

Аннотация. В данной статье описаны этапы развития бакши и национальной музыки в Каракалпакстане, новые образовательные учреждения в сфере культуры. Произведения народного искусства встречаются в золотом гусе народа, в его хранителях с давних времен, в исполнителях, в качестве начинки находятся сами люди.

Ключевые слова: фольклор, национальная музыка, жиров, бакши, дастан, теория, культура Каракалпакстана, национальный инструмент дуттар.

The term "folklore" itself refers to the concept, which means "the beneficiary of the population", "the essay of the population". That is why the population mouth two essays folklore that the island is among the three in most of the literature of the whole world. Written literature means the most headed branch of folkloric literature in the little-developed mardums. In addition, even because it is the literature that goes to the International of folklore has been, it is much more jiyi applied than written literature.

The reason is, in this case, the literacy of a person is in order to make the word chivalrous, piety, the story interesting to the fact that it is in the top position. Because of this, it developed much more widely than written literature. 100 volume Asik fairy tales, riddles, Proverbs, sayings, songs of the population, words, solt-program jirlari people's culture fund recorded by the population from behind the mouth. Still, with this saying that there are a lot of people, we can boast of the history of our dada ancestors in these epics, with more than 7-8 variants of each of our essays me, dástán and those epics.

Folklore art works by heart, and bittaew memorization Coast lives. They are known to be the coast of the printed word in recent centuries. In folklore, materials related to the history of each people, life expectancy, wishing goals, customs, solt-program, public development, concepts on the phenomena of human beings close to a person, the ratio of life expectancy to qorim, the philosophy of the people, etc., get a showy look. These works of art are the golden goose of the people, both those who have kept it since long periods, and the people themselves in the performers. The talant holders who came from among the people came to him from generation to generation. Over time, these works of fiction have both housed its early authors, and soon is interested in its distributors, performers with its early authors.

He was young to attend it at the expense of his own eyes, demands and wishes, changes compares, takes and adds, Well, they will become co-authors of works of art that they have completed at a certain level. When folklorism refers to the authors of works of art, it is imperative that we also take these cases into account. This is especially true of the three in fairy tales, epic, chants, which are large folkloric works of art. Ol large-scale species were not only literati, but also literate and uqibı boron tolanlı people. They are Zhirov-Bakhshis.

Folk art works are found in the golden goose of the people, in the keepers of it since long periods, in the performers, the people themselves are found as a stuffing. The tolan holders who came out of the midst of the people came to from generation to generation. They are different from others in their, the word, the cheekiness of execution.

This is folklore dastan is the only literati of the major species, this words-talakte are literate and master, let's mention the talented performers. They are Zhirov and Bakhshi. The word instrument Duwtar of the Bakhshi, their flanker, were the balabonists.

"Representing the nationality of the various peoples, their language and lifestyle, their program and Customs, the bakhshiqi art is an integral part of secular culture, valuable to all of us. These essays of World Cultural Heritage indicate that the historical talons of humanity, consequently, the future aspirations of representatives of different nationalities and nationalities are also common," said President Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

The epics of the population have not been exclusively love - tattoos, but a means of Culture, Knowledge, upbringing. In ancient times, when there were no written sources, the creative shores of our ancestors mouthpiece conveyed a sign of courage, goodness, honesty, patriotism, friendship from generation to generation. In that respect, the Bakhshi were and always were noble messengers. By the time of today's globalization, this historical art has gone unnoticed.

Due to the fact that the knowledge of the sagas of the old age goes beyond the Bakhshi, in many places these legacies were umitildi. He did not have time to pay attention to this area, Interest, Incentive. With the beginning of the leader of our country, the lowering of the bakhshimilar school in Surkhandarya has created good conditions for improving, maintaining and bringing to the present young generation of the same bakhshimilar sphere. On November 1, 2018, one more historical decision related to this area, was adopted gı degree "on holding an international festival of culinary arts".

The organizing committee was dotted and carried out extensive preparatory fists. The necessary conditions were created for Festival workers, Foreign mymans and spectators. The area around the Festival is decorated festively. The exhibition of exhibition, national style and costumes, oat and hand-held essays, more formal and approximate art essays, books, alboms, related to the art of bakhshism, has been worked.

The International Festival of culinary arts is held biennially, preserving the art of storytelling, bringing it to the generation of old, and broad publicke en joynirish serves to strengthen friendship and creative cooperation between nations and in this asnode. More than 160 representatives from 74 countries attended the festival in its first year.

The jirovs mostly performed the epics in the heroic contents. His instrument-qobiz. The epics "Alpamis", "Qoblan", "Qirq qiz", "Edige", common among the inhabitants of Karakalpak, spread to Mardum in the execution of Zhirovs and have survived to this day. In the repertoire of zhirovlarding was widely included in works of art of the jir, terma, Khirad-násiyat type. In the

international wide narrowed epics, you have one type Liro-Epos or opacity rags. Their performers are Bakhshi. The “Ġarip-Ashiq” whose transparent “Yusup Akhmed“,” Ashiq-Hámra " were narrowed and preserved in the execution of the Bakhshi.

The instrument of the Bakhshi were the dutor and their side by side . These historical legacies have come down to us from our ancestors, and so far the chivalric menen has been fulfilled. And how many ways are being carried out by our Lord mardum in order to develop this national heritage. As an example of this, on October 2, 2020, during a visit to Karakalpakstan, we noted the interest of Karakalpak youth in the field of bakhshism, attention, including the opening of the Nukus branch of the country Conservatory from Uzbekistan, including “children's opera and bakhshi” for Karakalpak children, in order to preserve karakalpak nationalism, give to the next generation after us. Soon after-white these things were realized.

Young children who have matured to the fact that they will have time for the sake of happiness have become lucky enough to sit in their parts, being among the most pioneers on September 6, 2021, of course, this opening was a big news in jú to the people of Karakalpak, we will be adaspagan. Currently, the children's opera and bakhshishılıq school is headed by the artist Daribay Khojanbergenov, who served Karakalpakstan.

This dargah mainly offers classes in bakhshism and opera. If we dwell on the sphere of bakhshiqi in the place of study, the direction of the field of good, the youth of talent enters the study and illuminates the performance skills in a short time on their qualifications. The young people are taught by Bakhshis of the population from Uzbekistan Zardaemuratov, Bakhshis Gulnara Allahmbergenova of the population of Karakalpakstan, laureate of the prize "Nihal" Turabekov Mukhammed, young Bakhshi Erisbay Asqarov and Maqset Ayyekeeov. Currently, classes are held in these educational institutions, in children's music schools, in bakhshiqi qanigeġi.

If you are studying the theoretical aspects of the culinary craft, the properties of which we are studying the theory of the status of our knowledge, download great lectures to music researchers and music connoisseurs, download them to the future national music, the theory at the craft of bakhshi, zhirov, applicantis introduced as a textbook of national music theory subjects to professionally give to the future generation, it is not possible to hear specialty classes to students would be appropriate. Of course many and researchers will bulur music researchers who have plenty of time and knowledge to develop this painstaking hot on the coast.

The number of music researchers who are currently studying at the Nukus branch of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan is low, we plan a lot of work in the development of the field of culture. In conclusion, we young music researchers, in turn, are in close contact with the Bakhshi and Jirovs, which are iconic to our people, trying to achieve results by studying the theory side of the population taronas.

REFERENCES

1. Q. Ayimbetov “Xalıq danalıġı” Nókis “Qaraqalpaqstan” 1988
2. Q. T.Adambaeva “Revalyuciyaga shekemgi qaraqalpaq muzıka tariyxı” “Qaralpaqstan” baspasi Nókis-1976
3. A.Nadirova “Qaraqalpaq muzıka tariyxı”

4. Муратбаева А. Актуальные вопросы совершенствования исполнительского мастерства в музыкальном искусстве: традиции и современность. Сборник материалов республиканской научно – практической конференции 10 мая 2022 года.
5. MURATBAEVA A. The influence of Karakalpak folk songs on the emergence of musical art //Young Scholar's Academic Journal. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 7. – С. 8-11.
6. MURATBAEVA A. Music born of the heart //International Research Conference on Business, Economics & Social Sciences. – 2023. – №. 10. – С. 3-5.
7. Axmetovna M. A. QARAQALPAQ MILLIY MUZÍKA MÁDENIYATÍN QÁLIPLESTIRIWDE FOLKLORLÍQ SHÍGARMALARDÍN HÁM ATQARÍWShÍLARDÍN ORNÍ //Innovations in Technology and Science Education. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 6. – С. 92-95.
8. Жумабаев А. Е. Творческий путь Сапарбая Палванова //Культура в фокусе научных парадигм [Текст]: / научн. ред. Муза Д. Е., Каика Н. Е. – Донецк: ДонНУ, 2023. – Вып. 16. – 388 с. – С. 32-36.